

Benchmarks for serving major technological areas in Cyber-Physical Energy System (CPES)

Cyber-Physical Energy System (CPES) incorporates multi-energy systems and communication domains which increases complexity and interdependency between domains and components for observability and controllability.

Overview of Benchmark Scenario

Benchmark configurations are very valuable instruments for providing a comparative assessment of new technological approaches and implementations.

Table 1 Overview of three benchmarks

Name	Domain	Simulation
Electrical Network	Electrical	MathWorks MATLAB/Simulink
Multi-Energy Networks	Electrical, Thermal	Pandapower, Modelica, Python
ICT-Enhanced Power System	Electrical, ICT	DIgSILENT PowerFactory, Mininet

Benchmark 1: Electrical Network

This benchmark represents a modern electrical system with a high penetration of power electronics converters and distributed energy generation from renewable sources.

Figure 1 Electrical Network Benchmark

Benchmark 2: Multi-Energy Networks

The second benchmark focuses on energy systems where multiple energy carriers are present.

Figure 2 Multi-Energy Network Benchmark

Benchmark 3: ICT-Enhanced Power Systems

The development of digitalisation of energy systems has increased the interactions between ICT and energy systems, and their interdependences.

Figure 3 ICT-Enhanced Power Systems

Further Reading

These three benchmarks are documented in detail following the PreCISE method and are available via ERIGrid 2.0 GitHub environment.

ERIGrid 2.0 project partners

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